

The role of the category of chance in the analysis of social relations

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Abstract

In the article, a number of opinions expressed by Abu Nasr Farabi and 20th century philosopher D.I. Shirokanov, among the ancient Central Asian philosophers, about the phenomenon of coincidence, as well as the study of coincidence together with the phenomena of necessity, causation and probability in synergetics, which is considered one of the modern philosophical teachings, because these phenomena are constantly one - some claim to be in touch. Also, specific conclusions were drawn regarding the concepts of synergetics, fluctuation, and bifurcation.

Key words: coincidence, necessity, synergetics, forecasting, fluctuation, bifurcation.

INTRODUCTION

Among the Eastern or Central Asian thinkers, Abu Nasr Farabi analyzes the category of chance in a meaningful way. The peculiarity of Farabi's worldview is that the scholar recognizes that random events are necessary and positive for the

life of a person and society: "If there were no random events in the world, the causes of which are unknown, there would be no feelings of fear, hope, and confidence (in a person). In turn, the absence of these leads to the complete loss of order and discipline both in human life and in the legal functioning of politics. Subjects who will not have anything tomorrow due to fear and lack of hope and trust will not obey their governors, and governors will not care about their subordinates. No one listens to Allah and (people) do not show kindness and mercy to each other. Because he who knows exactly what will happen tomorrow will try hard not to take advantage of that thing.¹

MAIN PART

It should be noted that this confession of Farabi helps us to understand the importance of coincidence and draw theoretical conclusions. If there were no accidents in the world, if everything was subject to legal necessity, the meaning of life would change. Life, according to Farabi, consists of contradictions, coincidences and contradictions. A person who overcomes these conditions can live in society. In particular, the activity of the mayor should be an example to others. If it has 12 senses, the management is good and accidents are avoided². Humans have always tried to overcome difficulties and problems. Although most of them could not get out of the hardships of life, but they connected the content of

¹ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ РОЛЬ ДИАЛЕКТИЧЕСКИХ КАТЕГОРИЙ В ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. Историческая психология и социология истории, 13 (1), 111-119.

² Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ РОЛЬ ДИАЛЕКТИЧЕСКИХ КАТЕГОРИЙ В ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. Историческая психология и социология истории, 13 (1), 111-119.

their whole life to the struggle against life's eddies. It is the faith and hope to get rid of the whirlwinds of life that inspired them to fight and live. Most of the people also hope that their lives will be improved by some coincidences.

Now, if we think about the negative consequences that occur due to the lack of fear mentioned by Farobi, it should be mentioned that the abstractness of the causes of many things in human life, including death, certain diseases and various disasters, makes a person alert in a sense. People fear Allah. Because no one knows what kind of days Allah will bring upon us tomorrow. All this ultimately leads people to respect the state system in which they live.

D.I., one of the philosophers who conducted significant scientific research on the role of the category of chance in scientific knowledge. Shirokanov has some interesting ideas about the category of chance. In particular, D.I. Shirokanov's "chance will always have its place in society. Because different and relatively independent events in it (society) inevitably crossed each other³ His conclusion is commendable. In fact, in all processes in all areas of society, one can see the phenomenon of chance to one degree or another. If we take as an example the political life of the society, or rather the activities of famous people who play a decisive role in political life, then it is necessary to note that, first of all, the appearance of every famous person is a random event. After all, any famous person is, first of all, a human being. We have analyzed in the previous parts of our scientific work that chance haunts every person throughout his life. So, chance shows its influence on society through human activities. D.I. Shirokanov writes on

³ Salimov, Bakhridin Lutfullaevich (2023). OPINIONS OF CENTRAL ASIAN SCHOLARS ON SOCIAL RELATIONS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3 (1-2), 178-182.

this topic: "If there is a need for a famous person, he is always found. The fact that he (the famous person) is that person, that he was born there and became a famous person is a coincidence. However, if there was no such famous person, surely another person would be found and could take his place, better or worse than him⁴. This opinion of D. I. Shirokanov corresponds to the process of self-organization in society in terms of its content. In our view, bringing a society from instability to a state of stability by celebrities is a form of self-organization. One can agree with many aspects of D.I. Shirokanov's opinion. After all, coincidences play an important role in the birth of any person, his career and the process of becoming a famous person. But in the absence of that well-known and famous person, we cannot say that someone else will definitely take his place. True, substitutes are always found to take the place of any famous person. But what will be the activity of these substitutes, there is a doubt that they will take the place of a famous person and become famous people themselves. In our opinion, D.I. Shirokanov took a model from the following opinion of F. Engels, one of the ideological leaders of the system he lived and created: "The appearance of this same famous person in a certain country at a certain time is nothing more than a pure coincidence," writes F. Engels. - But if we reject this person, there will be a need to replace him with another person, and such a replacement will be found immediately. It was something of a coincidence that Napoleon's ancestor of Corsica became the military dictator needed by the war-weary French Republic. But, if it were not for Napoleon, someone else would have played his role. This is proven by the fact that

⁴ Салимов Б.Л. Илмий билиш жараёнида тасодифнинг ўрни. Фалсафа фанлари номзоди диссертацияси. Алишер Навоий номли Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси(№417. Ю-34272/0). Тошкент. 2008, 144 б.

such a person was always found when needed."⁵ From these thoughts of F.Engels, it seems that the wrong conclusion was drawn that the deputy who would take Napoleon's place would also carry out Napoleon's policy. However, it is difficult to believe that Napoleon's successor, who by chance is never exactly the same in this world, could repeat Napoleon's actions in full, including re-establishing the monarchy in France or declaring war on Russia. In our opinion, when Napoleon Bonaparte did not take power in France in 1799, he was definitely replaced by another deputy. In it, we could see a relatively different image of France, Europe, and the whole world today. Our conclusion is that in place of any famous person, another substitute, maybe another famous person will be found. But then the historical development in that society, in that country, then in that region, and even in the whole world will take a different shape. According to V. P. Bransky, "there is also a possibility of turning prediction (prediction) into foretelling. In the language of physicists, it is also possible to confirm predictions on the basis of experiment, that is, scientific experience. If theory and practice coincide, then it can be considered that prophecy is confirmed. In this case, no one can prove that this is a coincidence. It is a social experiment and the whole history of the world embodies a chain of such experiments"⁶.

CONCLUSION

The application of theory to practice opens the door to not only telling, but also to the flourishing of human society. Of course, both theory and practice should

⁵ Lutfullaevich, Salimov B. "The Manifestation of Dialectical Principles in the Life of the Human and Society." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 05, 2020, pp. 112-117.

⁶ Салимов Б.Л. Илмий билиш жараёнида тасодифнинг ўрни. Фалсафа фанлари номзоди диссертацияси. Алишер Навоий номи Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси(№417. Ю-34272/0). Тошкент. 2008, 144 б.

acquire a positive character. But we must not forget that theory and practice do not always match. Their compatibility depends, first of all, on the extent to which that theory is developed. However, we must also remember that the complete predictability of one's life makes people bored. Because their lifestyles are the same. "If all the events in the world were fully predicted, there would be no uncertainties. As a result, there is no need to take any risk in the movement of people. Such a world would be defined in a strictly relational or homogeneous sense. Nothing new can be created in it. Everything is doomed to repeat itself forever in the same way".⁷ In short, the phenomenon of chance can be seen in the life of the society. Chance affects society through human activities.

REFERENCES

1. Салимов Б.Л. Илмий билиш жараёнида тасодифнинг ўрни. Фалсафа фанлари номзоди диссертацияси. Алишер Навоий номли Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси(№417. Ю-34272/0). Тошкент. 2008, 144 б.
2. Lutfullaevich, Salimov B. "The Manifestation of Dialectical Principles in the Life of the Human and Society." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 05, 2020, pp. 112-117.
3. Salimov, Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich (2023). OPINIONS OF CENTRAL ASIAN SCHOLARS ON SOCIAL RELATIONS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3 (1-2), 178-182.

⁷ Салимов Б.Л. Илмий билиш жараёнида тасодифнинг ўрни. Фалсафа фанлари номзоди диссертацияси. Алишер Навоий номли Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси(№417. Ю-34272/0). Тошкент. 2008, 144 б.

4. Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКАЯ РОЛЬ ДИАЛЕКТИЧЕСКИХ КАТЕГОРИЙ В ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. Историческая психология и социология истории, 13 (1), 111-119.